

Supplementary Material to the Paper

'Meeting the Inhabitants of X-ray Planet Krikkit: A Critical Analysis of the Distorted Wave Born Approximation'

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The text below was an outlook section of a manuscript which essentially contained a precursor version of reference 1 as the main part. References below to figures, sections smaller than 6 and formula numbers smaller than 40 refer to reference 1. This manuscript was used as an input to the artificial intelligence (AI) Claude Sonnet 4.6 (Anthropic) to generate the paper² 'Meeting the Inhabitants of X-ray Planet Krikkit: A Critical Analysis of the Distorted Wave Born Approximation'. Only small corrections were needed afterwards. The initial text below is provided as supplementary material to this paper.

6 Outlook

6.1 The Mezger Effect (ME)

The presented work is part of a series of papers to fence the Distorted Wave Born Approximation (DWBA)³⁻⁶. We emphasize, that the discussion is done With Due Respect for the Glorious X-Ray Community and their Great Achievements (WDRGXRCGA). The existence of a specific X-ray community results from the construction of synchrotrons as big-science facilities which are dedicated to the usage of X-rays. The DWBA describes the scattering at an interface. The vast majority of literature contributions relate the DWBA to small angle X-ray scattering³⁻⁶, where the small refractive index deviation (SRID) condition applies (see section 3.5). We just found one paper which denote their theoretical work on visible light as 'the DWBA'⁷. The identical name to the X-ray DWBA with insufficiently discussed limitations and differences rather produce ambiguity. A key point in the critical analysis concerns the approximations made in the DWBA and the way they are rather obscured. When you come from background in light scattering, you are used to relate the quality of a scattering theory to the conditions of the experiment you intend to describe. For the scattering of small particles in a bulk medium one has several theories, so Rayleigh scattering, Rayleigh-Gans theory, Mie scattering, or geometrical optics considerations⁸. Depending on the size of the particles relative to λ , the magnitude of the particles' refractive index (RI) contrast to the surrounding medium, and the question if the particles have an ideal symmetric shape like a sphere or not, you can choose the suitable approach. The derivation of these theories from the macroscopic Maxwell equations (MAME) involves approximations. The discussion of the approximations establishes the conditions where the theory is supposed to work properly. So, a well understood scattering theory contains clearly described conditions, typically in the form that a ratio of suitable parameters is assumed to be much smaller than 1. An argument, that a scattering theory is generally valid

simply for the reason that it is based on the MAME is inappropriate, as approximations are unavoidably involved. A medium which causes scattering is necessarily inhomogeneous, and there is no general theory for the propagation on electromagnetic radiation in an inhomogeneous medium. As interface scattering is rather more complicated than bulk scattering, one cannot expect that there is a single theory which works well for all possible conditions. So, with light scattering background, you typical have a relative approach to scattering theories.

There is a peculiar effect when you try to present a theoretical approach for visible light scattering in an interface layer, e.g. for the description of an evanescent Wave Dynamic Light Scattering (EWDLS) experiment^{9,10}. With high reproducibility there is an X-ray researcher in the audience who firmly insist that scattering at an interface would be a well understood topic within the DWBA. Such disputes become regularly quite heated. As an example, we report the most violent incidence which occurred during the spring conference of the German Physical Society 2019 in Regensburg. After a short presentation of a new extended transfer matrix approach (ETMA) for interface light scattering by the author¹¹, a heavy dispute was initiated by the chairman of the session, a X-ray researcher hosted at a Max Planck Institute (MPI). With pertinacious insistence, he claimed that the presented work would be the DWBA. Such a false priority claim is unexpected and bizarre, as the mathematical basis of the ETMA are 8×8 transfer matrices, interface bound fluctuations¹² (IBFs), and the layer scalar product¹³ (10), which stand clearly apart from the peculiar Green's function (GF) formalism of the DWBA. The dispute went as far as a strong claim by the chairman, that the DWBA would be suitable for birefringent samples. Such a claim is not justified from the literature situation. Mathematics is the language of physics, and a reliable use of references is an essential pillar of science. The disrespect of these elements for the sake of a chorus of praise for the DWBA renders a scientific discussion impossible. The heavy dispute did not only impede the present work and the ETMA, it also impaired the reputation of the related MPI, as it raises doubts on a proper implementation of scientific culture there. Furthermore,

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it is uncommon that experimental physicists advertise a theory. WDRGXRCGA, we address such reproducible irrational and ruthless attacks on theoretical interface light scattering approaches by DWBA-sticklers as *Mezger effect* (ME). The perception as systematic effect allows a neutral description similar to the documentation of experimental findings, of course within the WDRGXRCGA approach.

6.2 The Formidable Ambiguity Criterion (FAC) in the DWBA Literature

Standard text about the DWBA like “X-ray and neutron scattering from rough surfaces”³, “Scattering of X-rays and neutrons at interfaces”⁴, “X-ray and Neutron Reflectivity: Principles and Applications”¹⁴, or “Probing surface and interface morphology with Grazing Incidence Small Angle X-Ray Scattering”⁶ make explicit reference to X-rays and partially neutrons in their titles and restrict the description to such radiation. What is missing, however, are sufficiently clear discussions in these texts of settings and approximations which are specific to X-rays in contrast to visible light. This deficiency in combination with the titles leads to a vagueness of the DWBA literature. With high appreciation for the X-ray community, we introduce the term formidable ambiguity criterion (FAC) for the assignment of the DWBA to X-rays without a proper discussion.

A consequence of this peculiar state is that there are two ways to read the DWBA literature. When you come from optics, the message of the titles appears to indicate, that there is no claim at all that such a theory is considered adequate to describe scattering experiments based on visible light. It is the critical access to the DWBA literature. On the other hand, the ME shows, that the approach of a sizable number of X-ray researchers is quite opposite. It appears that the absence of a sufficiently clear discussion of approximations and prerequisites of this theory within the DWBA literature encourages them to raise a claim, that the DWBA would be suitable for general conditions, as if it would be a fundamental theory. It is the opportunistic access to the DWBA literature, which is based on a strong positive bias towards the DWBA. WDRGXRCGA, we introduce the term Bias Opportunism Correlation (BOC) for the mindset of a community who kind of blindly assumes that their favorite theory necessarily has to be a very good one without a proper analysis in the literature and thus without any understanding of the theory’s limitations. The ME and the BOC appear to be two sides of the same coin, which mutually involve and reinforce each other. This connection yields a direct explanation of the remarkable reproducibility of the ME. Any approach for a theoretical description of interface scattering for visible light, no matter how it is actually set up, directly disturbs the comfort zone inherently contained in the BOC mindset and thus induces the ME. There are two mutually exclusive options: either the DWBA literature which fails to clarify the FAC is considered as great immaculate science. For a stabilization of such a perception, it is required that the X-ray community permanently blocks a theory for interface scattering of visible light. Alternately, the FAC is properly resolved and the DWBA is definitely banned to the X-ray corner of electromagnetic radiation, so

the well deserved space for a interface light scattering theory is granted and can be protected against DWBA-campaigners. The ME indicates the heated discussion on which of these two options is appropriate. The key problem here is that the vague DWBA literature is basically useless to resolve the conflict.

The same problem arises when the DWBA is mentioned in the introduction of a manuscript for a new theory on interface scattering of visible light. It is fair and appropriate to mention it. However, as the literature state about the prerequisites and limitations of the DWBA is in such a poor state, it is not feasible to discuss any differences to a new approach. It is essentially impossible to compare a new theory to an undefined botch. Thus, the two possible ways to read the DWBA literature induce quite different assessments. Within their opportunistic viewpoint, the X-ray community is eager to consider the DWBA a great theory. Within the critical approach, on the other hand, the DWBA appears as a honorable piece of X-ray folklore which turns out to be an essential plug for a proper understanding of the physics of scattering phenomena at an interface. It is the undefined vagueness of the FAC which makes the DWBA such a horrible persistent plug.

It is important at this spot to acknowledge the detailed and complex discussion of the literature concerning interface scattering of X-rays in the extensive review article by Renaud et al.⁶. This plethora of contributions referring explicitly to X-rays does not resolve the FAC.

A clarification of the FAC is found below, in section 6.8.

6.3 The First Key Question

A key issue at this point is the question, who is responsible to resolve the FAC? Who is in charge to carve out the specific properties and restrictions of the DWBA? An answer is easier in the neighboring discipline mathematics, which is partly the idealistic role model for physics. In mathematics, terms and quantities are defined rigorously and it is clearly the duty of a scientist who establishes a theory or mathematical sentence to provide a mathematical prove for it. A proper definition of terms and quantities is an essential basis of all science.

The situation in physics is not as clear. Partly there are physics theories which are closely related to mathematics and are based on proper mathematical proofs. Often, it is required to specify ideal conditions or slight deviations from it. These are the approximations within a theory. Implicit to such mathematics oriented approach is the assignment of responsibility in the same way as in mathematics. So, an unambiguous introduction of terms and quantities, a proper discussion of mathematical transformations and a clear statement of approximations is usually reliably provided by those scientists who set up a mathematics oriented physics theory. Older physics theories sometimes do not resolve their tricky approaches, so the limitations and approximations are not disclosed properly. Furthermore there are effective physics theories which also describe experiments well. Typically they are clearly indicated as toy models or by similar terms. The paucity of a proper discussion of the approximations in the DWBA literature in combination with an absence of a clarification, if the DWBA is

meant to be a mathematics oriented physics theory or rather an effective theory which somehow describes X-ray scattering data, constitutes the FAC. If the DWBA literature is interpreted similar to a mathematics text, the reference to X-rays in the title should be read as a prerequisite of the involved content. So, from a mathematical point of view, DWBA-campaigners should remain in their X-ray regime and strictly stay out of a discussion of interface light scattering theory.

It is worth to scrutinize the DWBA literature for traces of a discussion of approximations or limitations. The search reveals the announcement of Baumbach and Milkulik within the textbook edited by Daillant and Gibaud¹⁴, that the DWBA would be a “semi-dynamical” theory. However, no proper definition of such a term or literature reference is found within the entire book. Furthermore, there is no mathematical proof, that the DWBA would fulfill the criterion as a semi-dynamical theory. It is unclear, which value of such an undefined and not proven announcement there is for X-ray experiments. For the question if the DWBA would be suitable for optics experiments, the statement is useless, at best. We recover the same vagueness of the DWBA literature which is already found in the FAC. These ambiguities indicate, that the DWBA does not qualify as a rigorously mathematically founded theory.

The DWBA furthermore involves Born’s approximation or a perturbation approach. The former is even contained of the theory’s name. Physics students typically become used to these approaches within a course on quantum mechanics. So, they are honorable pieces of physics. It should be pointed out, however, that these methods are not of mathematical origin. So, they do not provide axiomatic results when suitable prerequisites are fulfilled. From a theoretical point of view, a discussion of conditions where such methods are promising would be required. At this point, the DWBA literature has its weakness, unfortunately. For the further discussion, we introduce the term Ultra-Physics (UP) or formalism physics for theories which employ equations on a formalistic way without a proper discussion of the involved symbols and conceptions or which blindly rely on Born’s approximation or a perturbation theory, without an analysis under which conditions these physics-based approaches are reasonable. The lack of such a discussion leads to a confusing intermixing of proper mathematical conclusions and physics arguments.

The tiny deviation of the X-ray RI from the vacuum value 1 in (31) is the SRID condition, which is already addressed in the introduction. Unfortunately, the DWBA literature mentions it only casually. One can get the impression that a discussion if the SRID condition is an essential input for the DWBA is intentionally avoided. When you find a literature spot where the SRID is briefly addressed as a condition for the DWBA, like before equation (4.5) in⁵, you better mark it directly, as it is very difficult to find it back in the running text. A further hint to the SRID condition is hidden in the derivation of a RI for X-rays by F. de Bergevin in chapter 1 of the textbook (see the discussion of (1.73) in¹⁵). Any further derivation based on the RI obtained in this way is subject to the SRID condition as well. We will see below (see sections 6.6–6.8) that arguments based on oscillating electrons which are inspired by the construction of the X-ray RI are repeatedly em-

ployed in the DWBA. One can expect the same SRID restriction for these arguments as for the X-ray RI. Unfortunately, a corresponding clarification is absent in the textbook¹⁴.

The RI contrast $\Delta n = n_1 - n_2$ results as the difference of two RI values n_1 and n_2 . For X-rays, the contrast is of order 10^{-6} , in case one of the RI values concerns the vacuum (see (31)). The subtraction of two positive δ -values for other cases leads to an even smaller contrast. For comparison, we consider the visible light RI values $n_0 = 1.33$ of water and $n_2 = 1$ of air. These media form an interface, which can be illuminated from the water side¹⁶. The example shows, that the visible light contrast at an interface is of order 1, i.e. 10^6 times higher than a X-ray contrast.

A further consequence of the difference in contrast concerns RI-gradients dn/dz which scale with Δn . They can be compared to typical values of the scattering vector magnitude $q \sim 2\pi n\lambda^{-1}$. An example for visible light is the RI profile in Fig. 6A. The gradient is directly visible in the figure and one has $dn/dz \gg q$. For this condition, RI-fluctuations due to inhomogeneities in an interface structure imply fluctuations in the RI gradient. The discussion in section 2 has outlined, that the gradient effects are hidden in the unsteady boundary conditions for p-polarization. As a consequence, the ETMA contain a contribution of gradient fluctuations to the scattering signal which involve p-polarization of incident or scattered light. For X-rays, in contrast, the RI profile hardly deviates from 1. On a linear scale which starts from 0, the X-ray RI essentially looks like a straight constant line of value 1. So one finds the opposite case $dn/dz \ll q$ for X-rays. For X-rays it does not matter that the DWBA does not take gradient fluctuations into account.

Furthermore, the DWBA’s description of polarization effects appears to apply only for small angle scattering, which is used in Grazing Incidence Small Angle Scattering (GISAXS). A corresponding very brief remark is found in the review article by Renaud et al.⁶ at the end of the paragraph after their equation (76). Such subliminal insinuations generate the impression of opportunism within the X-ray community towards the DWBA. A proper presentation would clarify with sufficient visibility, that the polarization description in the DWBA is unreliable and thus essentially useless for advanced polarization dependent measurements like scattering ellipsometry. Instead of such a clear and critical description, the DWBA is presented as a great theory and its limitations are addressed only in a rather secretive style. Such a biased discussion constitutes the BOC.

Although the DWBA literature unfortunately fails to discuss the tiny contrast and negligible RI gradient for X-rays properly, it appears that these elements are the essential simplifications. It is these elements which make the DWBA to provide reasonable predictions for X-rays. These elements are probably the reason, why the titles of the literature contributions relate the DWBA to X-rays. Here, we switch perspective to an experimental verification of a theory. It is acknowledged, that the DWBA is widely used and successful theory for X-rays. Such a finding, however, by no means support a claim that the DWBA would be suitable for visible light interface scattering experiments. It does not matter how many X-ray experiments with tiny contrast and negligible RI-gradient confirm the DWBA, a claim that the DWBA would predict

experimental results for high contrast and interfaces with significant RI gradient, as it is found for visible light, cannot be drawn from these X-ray experiments. So, from an experimental point of view, DWBA-adherers should remain in their X-ray regime and strictly stay out of a discussion of interface light scattering measurements. It is highly unfortunate, that the SRID condition is not discussed properly in the DWBA literature. There is a correlation between the ignorance of DWBA-campaigners about the SRID condition and this literature state.

Sure enough, the situation looks quite different from the opportunistic viewpoint. It appears that the X-ray community generally accepts that the DWBA literature fails to clarify the theory's approximations, the role of the SRID conditions and the negligible RI gradient for X-rays. The X-ray community pushes the analysis of these issues outside their business. The assignment of responsibility is opposite to the situation in mathematics. Due to the long tradition to use the DWBA, they want to consider it a great theory and rather discard the DWBA's issues. With their majority due the funding fortune for X-ray methods based on synchrotron big-science facilities, the X-ray community appears to strive for a general hegemony of their limited DWBA-approach to interface scattering theory.

The general weakness to handle approximations and conceptions within the DWBA concerns the absence of a proper literature discussion as well as an understanding that approximations and conceptions cannot be undone at a latter state of a discussion. The latter point is applicable no matter if the approximations are discussed explicitly, or when they are hidden with only a hint in the titles of the contributions. The perception of the DWBA as a fundamental theory clearly is an over-interpretation. The author happens to know Jean Daillant from the SOMATAI initial training network, so one of the editors of the textbook¹⁴. We are convinced, that he would not support an over-interpretation of his textbook by a giddy transfer of the DWBA to interface light scattering. It is not by accident that he had consciously decided to indicate X-rays in the book's title. Unfortunately, the book does not provide a clarifying spot which can be held under the very nose of a MPI X-ray researcher with opportunistic DWBA-perception who attacks a new visible light interface scattering approach. Instead, the MPI DWBA-campaigner argues that the DWBA is a great theory, simply for the reason that it is described in a textbook¹⁴. The approach that the content of a book is to be believed in for the sake of its own is unsuitable for a scientific question. Such an approach, however, is wide-spread in a religious context. There is no wonder, that a discussion about the DWBA rather resembles a religious dispute than a proper scientific discussion. With a clear literature situation, such a dispute would not occur. The outline here elucidates the BOC's feed-back loop between the over-estimation of the DWBA and poor literature discussion of its prerequisites and approximations.

This present discussion and further contributions compile the issues and limitations of the DWBA. Thus, we gain the scientific control over the DWBA. The purpose is to overcome the ME in the future. Any thoughtless argument that scattering at an interface has to be considered a well understood and completely solved topic simply for the reason that the DWBA is described in

a textbook can be countered with a hint to this work and follow-up contributions. While the X-ray literature fails to indicate the DWBA's limitations, complementary clarifying literature becomes available. The approach is a scientific unfriendly take-over of the DWBA. It is highly unfortunate that such a step is necessary, as it should have been in the responsibility of the X-ray community to resolve the DWBA's issues by themselves a long time ago. The author would strongly prefer to focus on interface light scattering. As, however, the number superiority of DWBA-advocators based on the power-funding of X-ray methods within synchrotron big-science facilities is so bone-crushing, a fencing of the DWBA is apparently unavoidable before a discussion of a more general interface scattering theory. Still, it is essential to emphasize that this capture of the DWBA is done within the WDRGXRCGA-approach. It is acknowledged that the DWBA is an effective theory for X-rays with a long honorable tradition of usage for GISAXS measurements. What is resolved is the unclear FAC. We foster the message of the titles of DWBA literature, that the DWBA is useful only for X-ray measurements.

6.4 The Special Role of a Scattering Theory

As a rule of thumb it could be said, that theorists are generally convinced that their theories are great. It is up to experimental scientists to check, if such a great theory is actually useful to describe experiments and thus the real world. Apart from some theoretical speculations for conditions far away for length and energy scales not accessible to terrestrial experiments or astronomical observations, or other theoretical assumptions not compatible with the real world, this division of labor is a well established and reasonable procedure in physics. The role of numerical mathematics and computer experiments in simulations can be assigned to such a scheme. So, theoretical work is done by theorists who typically have a better knowledge of advanced theoretical methods and, in particular, who are aware of the necessity to indicate approximations properly. Experimental scientists, on the other hand, have specialized knowhow on how to run experiments including data evaluation and model fitting. Examples of such practical knowhow concern the subtraction of detector dark counts or experience on which scattering angles provide reliable data and which other angles are affected by the tail of the direct beam or a beam stop. While such experience is typically not documented with the same accuracy as a mathematical theory, it is essential for successful experimental work. Like the synergy in interdisciplinary science, the collaboration between theory and experiment produces added value. It is a sound approach, that the experimental cross-check of a theory is in general not done by the very same authorities who have set up the theory.

When it comes to scattering experiments, however, the separation is not as clear. Scattering is an indirect method. One needs a theoretical modeling of the propagation of the used radiation to make predictions or model fits for scattering experiments¹⁷. An example for an interface experiment is the scattering of a polymer brush. A theory for the brush has to be combined with an interface scattering theory for a theoretical modeling. Without such a modeling or a model fit, a scattering experiment is half blind and

often not able to provide quantitative results. Thus, there is a key role of the scattering theory for advanced scattering experiments. The modeling of experiments is in fact the main application of any scattering theory. Conventional theorists, however, are typically mainly interested in the system they describe, so in our example the polymer brush. So, it is the experimentalists themselves who build up the scattering theory. It appears reasonable to relate the scattering theory to the practical experimental knowhow on data treatment and model fitting. Such an approach could provide a simple solution for the dispute about the DWBA. In the same way as X-ray sources and X-ray detectors are not suitable for light scattering experiments, the specific X-ray data treatment and practical knowhow cannot be simplistically transferred to optical experiments. The notion of the DWBA as a part of the practical knowhow supports the claim, that DWBA-sticklers should stay out from any discussion of interface scattering of visible light. The poor indication of approximations in the DWBA matches in fact the lack of a systematic description of the X-ray specific practical knowhow.

The opportunistic approach certainly comes to a different conclusion. As the description of the DWBA involves the MAME, the DWBA-maintainers appear to assume that their theory could be applied to any electromagnetic radiation. The discussion in section 6.1 shows, that such a naive viewpoint is not justified. Unavoidably there are approximations and simplifying assumptions in any scattering theory. They cannot be undone in retrospect. So, it is not possible to extend a theory based on certain approximations at a later state to other conditions which are incompatible with the approximations. However, due to the insufficient discussion in the DWBA literature, the DWBA-campaigners are not aware of the involved approximations. This setting forms the stage for the ME.

We start with a look at this stage from the perspective of light scattering. This technique is also an indirect method. A theory is needed which describes reliably the interface scattering for visible light. The relation to X-rays in the titles of the DWBA literature and the not clarified approximations exclude the DWBA. However, any attempt for a theory beyond the DWBA reproducibly leads to the ME and a conflict with the X-ray community. It appears that they equalize any approach with an alleged criticism of their DWBA. It is the fatal effect of the BOC's feedback loop. As the role of approximations and their limiting effect on a theory are so poorly discussed in the DWBA literature, a sizable number of X-ray researchers appears to assume that there is automatically a mathematical identity to the more generalized theory. After all, the DWBA is described in a textbook, and this is considered a suitable argument that it has to be a very good theory. They fight for the DWBA as their traditional interface scattering theory, so their essential theoretical tool to predict, interpret and analyze GISAXS experiments.

Here, however, there is a misunderstanding. The creation of a more general interface scattering theory is required for description of interface light scattering with much higher contrast. It is not the purpose to criticize the DWBA. We acknowledge that it is a traditional theory to describe interface scattering of X-rays, where the SRID condition is fulfilled. So, the X-ray community

can continue to celebrate their hyped DWBA for their purposes. There is a poor analysis and documentation of the approximations, however, the historical usage up to this point has shown, that the DWBA is useful for X-rays up to the accuracy typically needed.

For a resolution of the disputes about the DWBA, we suggest to re-establish the conventional complementary roles of theory and experiment. Strictly! In our example from above, a scattering experiment tests both: the interface scattering theory and the theory on the polymer brush. So, experimentalists should consider it as an advantage when a competing interface scattering theory is established. X-ray experimentalists had set up their DWBA themselves and thus might have the typical positive bias of theorists. Still, a reaction within a ME to alternative theoretical approaches is by no means appropriate.

6.5 Development Toward the DWBA

The DWBA evolved from a predecessor theory which the X-ray community refers to as the Born Approximation (BA)¹⁷. This nomenclature is poorly chosen, as it conflicts with Born's approximation as a general approximation scheme used, for instance, in the description of bulk scattering^{8,18}. Simply calling a theory for interface scattering "BA" constitutes confusing terminology. The DWBA appears as an improved BA which, on one hand, describes X-ray GISAXS data better, but on the other hand is even more opaque than the BA.

For bulk scattering described by Born's approximation, it is well established that fluctuations must have low contrast to be adequately described^{8,18,19}. For larger fluctuations, multiple scattering occurs. In light scattering, experimental techniques exist to isolate single scattering contributions, such as two-color cross-correlation Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) or 3D cross-correlation DLS^{20,21}. Multiple scattering is also discussed as a problem in bulk X-ray scattering²².

In contrast to bulk scattering, reflection phenomena, e.g. described by Fresnel reflection coefficients, exhibit a different dependency on λ . At fixed contrast, the amplitude of bulk scattering is proportional to λ^{-2} (and thus intensity proportional to λ^{-4} , the well-known explanation for the blue sky)⁸. When transitioning from visible light to X-rays, the contrast becomes much smaller. This has the consequence that despite the strong λ -dependence, scattering investigations can be conducted with both, visible light and X-rays. Through the variation of wavelength and contrast, conditions exist in both wavelength regimes that can be described by single scattering and that yield sufficient signal for experimental investigations.

Reflection, on the other hand, is independent of λ at constant contrast, exhibiting λ^0 behavior²³. For light with strong contrast, reflection is always important; for X-rays, however, it is not. This corresponds to common knowledge that X-rays normally pass through all materials, which is not the case for visible light.

In a theory for scattering in an averaged RI profile at an interface, propagation in the RI profile and scattering at fluctuations of the profile are intermixed. At constant contrast of the profile, propagation essentially exhibits the λ^0 behavior of Fresnel coeffi-

cients, while scattering at fluctuations shows the λ^{-2} behavior of bulk scattering. This is complex and means that a naive transfer of a theory fully based on Born's approximation that works in the X-ray regime is not expected to succeed for visible light.

Historically, when the BA was established, this was not properly discussed^{3,14,17}. The BA applies Born's approximation to both the reflection component and the scattering at fluctuations (inhomogeneities). Without adequate discussion, a language is established that describes both reflection and scattering at inhomogeneities as scattering. This renders the term multiple scattering imprecise, as it is no longer clear whether it refers to multiple reflections in an RI profile (which can be envisioned as a sequence of layers with constant RI and treated with the matrix method²³), or to multiple scattering at inhomogeneities. For X-ray scattering this approach is viable, as all contrasts are very small. However, the role of contrast in the BA is not properly discussed. While it is well established for bulk scattering that the use of Born's approximation requires very small contrast^{8,19}, this prerequisite is not explicitly stated for the BA. Through the conception and language that treats reflection like scattering, this theory is implicitly restricted to low contrast and thus to X-ray scattering. This restriction, however, is not clearly articulated in the literature.

It became apparent that the BA does not function adequately near the critical angle for total reflection^{4,24}. At this angle, the reflected and transmitted wave amplitudes become comparable, and the simple perturbation approach of the BA breaks down. As a remedy, the DWBA was developed, which incorporates the reflection and refraction in a stratified medium exactly through distorted waves, while treating scattering from inhomogeneities as a perturbation^{3,4}. By name, the DWBA would still be a Born approximation, but in reality it is rather a perturbation theory starting from a non-perturbed system¹⁷. Born's approximation has the advantage from the perspective of applied mathematics that it at least established that the perturbation must be small²⁵. Perturbation theory, in contrast, relies without explicit control on the assumption that the unperturbed and perturbed systems are somehow similar. Consequently, clear criteria for when contrast should be considered small become even less transparent. The X-ray community appears to assume that contrast plays no significant role, as if the DWBA had been rigorously derived from the MAME without approximations. For X-rays, the DWBA successfully remedies the previous problems of the BA near the critical angle¹⁷. For the X-ray community, the DWBA therefore appears to be a major achievement, and there is understandably a strong positive reception toward it. However, the prerequisites already insufficiently discussed in the BA become even more obscure in the DWBA.

With a sober view, it can be stated that the DWBA is an effective theory that describes X-ray data but is inadequately discussed in terms of its underlying approximations and thus incompletely understood. Due to the very small contrast for X-rays, RI gradients are essentially negligible. The DWBA incorporates propagation and scattering in gradient-free profiles including refraction. Additionally, scattering measurements at interfaces are not performed on an absolute scale; there is always a free scaling factor. Real X-ray measurements can thus be adjusted or fitted to the

theory under these circumstances. It must be acknowledged that the DWBA is an effective theory for GISAXS and similar experiments, and there is a tradition of the DWBA in the X-ray regime that deserves recognition WDRGXRCGA. However, this is no reason to naively apply the DWBA to higher contrast conditions as encountered in light scattering, or to attribute to it a fundamental character that would make it universally applicable across the electromagnetic spectrum.

6.6 Poorly discussed Reciprocity Theorem (RT) of the DWBA

Different approaches to establish the MAME starting from the microscopic Maxwell Equations (MIME) have been outlined in section 2.3 of reference 2. The character of the current density \vec{j} in the X-ray approaches remains unclear. Although current densities are present in the MIME as well as in the MAME, they are of different nature. An attempt to describe electromagnetism in matter based on the MIME has to take all charges into account. Their movements builds up the microscopic current density. In contrast, the MAME within optics literature introduce the polarization \vec{P} of atoms or molecules²⁶. This meaning of the symbol \vec{P} is very well established over a long time in the optics literature. Oscillations of bound electrons in the electromagnetic field are contained in \vec{P} . For real relative permittivity (RP), the bound electrons oscillate in phase with \vec{E} , or with a phase shift of 180°. In addition, the MAME contain a density of free charges ρ_{free} and their current density \vec{J}_{free} . These free charges are ions in a solution or conducting electrons in a metal. They are not attached to a molecule. In a dielectric material, ρ_{free} and \vec{J}_{free} are zero and one has real-valued RI and RP. For other cases and non-zero frequency, the concept of the generalized electric displacement field (GEDF)²⁷ can be applied. It absorbs \vec{J}_{free} and eliminates ρ_{free} from the MAME on a mathematical basis. So, a system with free charges and currents is mapped to a charge free system. The transformation brings up an imaginary part for the RP proportional to the conductivity σ . The latter quantity originates from the constitutive relation (CR)

$$\vec{J}_{\text{free}} = \sigma \vec{E}. \quad (40)$$

As \vec{J}_{free} and \vec{E} are in phase, there is a positive time average of $\vec{J}_{\text{free}} \cdot \vec{E}$. The approach is highly satisfactory, as it explains absorption as a loss by free currents. Furthermore, there is a phase shift of 90° between \vec{J}_{free} and ρ_{free} in an oscillation, and so the same shift between \vec{E} and ρ_{free} . So, the difference between oscillating electrons which belong to P and those which take part in \vec{J}_{free} is the phase relation relative to \vec{E} . In addition to the ions in solutions and conduction electrons, ρ_{free} and \vec{J}_{free} contain also bound electrons which are excited by ω and thus suffer a phase shift relative to \vec{E} . When using a complex RP which involves a complex RI, it makes no sense to discuss ρ_{free} and \vec{J}_{free} as independent extra quantities. A mathematics oriented optics approach considers the MIME and the MAME as separated systems of equations with constituents of different character. Apart from the derivation of the MAME from the MIME, an intermixing of these separated systems makes no sense and is problematic.

On this basis, we investigate the reciprocity theorem (RT) of the DWBA. It is used to establish the required Green's function.

Although it is a central element, some DWBA contributions⁶ do not provide a derivation. Instead, they refer to the textbook of Dailant and Gibaud¹⁴, where an apparent derivation is hidden in appendix 4.A. WDRGXRCGA it can be noted, that there is a remarkable discrepancy between the BOC and the strong belief in the DWBA within the X-ray community on one hand and the poor mathematical foundation on the other hand.

The RT is employed to replace the propagation of radiation from the scattering event to the detector by an inverse propagation from the detector to the scattering event. So, one compares two systems of electromagnetic fields with their related currents. They are distinguished by the index A and B . Following Landau and Lifschitz (see §69 in²⁸), a first RT is derived, which reads

$$\int d^3r \vec{E}_B \cdot \vec{J}_A = \int d^3r \vec{E}_A \cdot \vec{J}_B. \quad (41)$$

This result is obtained on the basis of the MAME. Accordingly, the current densities \vec{J}_A and \vec{J}_B designate free currents. As a consequence, the value of (41) is rather limited from the viewpoint of visible light optics. For dielectrics, one has $\vec{J}_A = \vec{J}_B = 0$ and (41) is fulfilled trivially. The same applies, when one eliminates the free currents based on the GEDF²⁷. This concept requires $\omega \neq 0$. Only for electrostatics or magneto-statics with $\omega = 0$ there is a non-trivial meaning of (41). Even when one rejects the GEDF, the usage of (41) as a starting point for a scattering theory is a rather weird approach. As an illustration, we consider the scattering of dielectric colloidal particles dispersed in water. The water contains some ions, and their movements constitutes the free currents. There is, however, basically no scattering contrast of the ions to the surrounding water, at least for visible light. Instead, scattering is caused by the colloidal particles, which are not involved in the free currents. The example shows, that a scattering theory founded on free currents and (41) is a conceptual mismatch.

The usage of currents in X-ray theories appears to originate from the construction of a RI for X-rays (see section 2.3 of reference 2). Instead of a discussion based on the RI or the RP, the DWBA continues to use the currents by oscillating electrons appropriate to a microscopic picture to describe scattering effects. There is a clear difference to optics, which involves a hierarchical approach. The foundation of the MAME starting from the MIME and thereby the introduction of a RP and a RI are considered separately in optics. Scattering theories are then based exclusively on the MAME and the CRs. The conceptual clarity of such an approach is an essential advantage.

Similar benefits are discussed in computer science within the Don't Repeat Yourself (DRY) approach²⁹. The maintenance of computer code is simplified essentially, when important steps are encoded only once, and a scattering of similar tasks in a huge computer code is avoided. Computer code which does not fulfill the DRY criterion is designated as WET. Also mathematical proofs typically involve a similar economic hierarchical approach and do not repeat similar steps over and over. The DWBA, in contrast, intermixes by its reference to microscopic currents a macroscopic picture with averaged properties and the microscopic behavior of the electrons. It is a WET theory. It is in particular problematic,

that the DWBA literature does not provide a clear discussion, that the X-ray specific construction of the RI is frequently used in theoretical steps, in particular for the derivation of the RT in appendix 4.A of¹⁴. This approach restricts the theory to X-rays, whereas, however, DWBA-advocators are not informed properly about this limitation by the poor discussion in the DWBA-literature.

To illustrate the conceptual problem of the intermixing of microscopic and macroscopic properties in the DWBA, we recall that the vacuum speed of light c is related to a MIME description which does not contain a RP or a RI. On the other hand, the light propagation in a medium of refractive index n within a MAME-description amounts to c/n . There is no problem in this difference as long as one consistently uses either a MAME or a MIME description. As the DWBA intermixes both description, things become ambiguous and opaque. However, there is no corresponding discussion in the DWBA literature. Again, the X-ray community pushes this issue outside their business and persistently assumes that the DWBA is a great theory. It is once more the SRID condition for X-rays with n very close to 1 which gets things to work for X-rays, as this case engenders $c \approx c/n$.

The intermixing appears to originate from a schizophrenic approach in X-ray theory. On one hand, they need a RI to account for the observed total reflection (TR) (total external reflection) for grazing incidence, on the other hand they want to stick to a microscopic picture with oscillating electrons emitting dipole radiation. The DWBA schizophrenia shows up also in another inconsistency. The derivation of the propagation equation (4.3) in⁵ very briefly mentions that no charges and currents are assumed. This spot is consistent with optics literature (see the beginning of this section 6.6): for the derivation of the wave equation, one has to set $\rho_{\text{free}} = 0$ and $\vec{J}_{\text{free}} = 0$. Later, however, the derivation of the RT is based on currents. There is no discussion of the discrepancy. Rather, the DWBA follows an opportunistic UP approach. When it is suitable to set the currents equal to zero they are dropped, otherwise currents are considered with an easy-going but problematic intermixing of microscopic oscillating electrons and macroscopic free currents.

The DWBA approach is not suitable for visible light with large deviation of n from 1. In the optics description, an electromagnetic wave in a medium is a combined excitation of the fields and the medium polarization. This coupling yields the propagation speed c/n . The microscopic fields in atoms and molecules are much stronger than the perturbation by the wave. Also the incident field propagates with c/n . The X-ray conception with quasi-free electrons which are shaken by an incident microscopic wave propagating with c is not compatible with the requirements for visible light. A further ambiguity in a theory based on currents is their opposite direction in the two approaches to establish a RI for X-rays (see discussion in section 2.3 of reference 2). Although the DWBA extensively uses currents, their direction and conceptual nature is far from clear and a discussion is absent.

The derivation of the RT in the DWBA textbook¹⁴ continues with an abrupt appearance of the following relation:

$$\vec{P} = \frac{1}{i\omega} \vec{J}. \quad (42)$$

This equation appears in the floating text and has no number in⁵. It does not fit to the framework of classical electromagnetism. There is no connection like (42) between the polarization and the free current. The issue is not discussed further in the textbook. The accompanying text denotes the symbol \vec{P} in (42) as dipole density (DD). Obviously, it is a deviation from the very well established usage of the symbol \vec{P} for the polarization. We used a software to view a pdf file to search for other occurrences of the term DD in the textbook and found only 2 spots in the caption of Fig. 4.1. There is neither a claim that the DD would be the same as the polarization, nor a discussion of differences of the two quantities. Rather, (42) appears to be the definition of the DD. The division by $i\omega$ on the right side of (42) corresponds to an integration over the frequency dependent current density of unclear nature (see discussion above). The DWBA literature is highly vague at this point, and (41) and (42) cannot constitute a proof of the RT for the case of visible light.

The final RT of the DWBA

$$\int d^3r \vec{E}_B \cdot \vec{P}_A = \int d^3r \vec{E}_A \cdot \vec{P}_B \quad (43)$$

is obtained from (41) with (42) by a replacement of \vec{J}_A and \vec{J}_B by \vec{P}_A and \vec{P}_B , respectively.

We had suggested a much simpler derivation for (43)³⁰. With the CR $\vec{D} = \epsilon_0 \vec{E} + \vec{P} = \epsilon_0 \vec{E} + \vec{P}$ for the dielectric displacement field \vec{D} , a one line transformation yields

$$\vec{E}_B \cdot \vec{P}_A = \underbrace{\vec{E}_B \epsilon_0 \vec{E}_A}_{\vec{D}_A} - \epsilon_0 \vec{E}_A \vec{E}_B = \vec{E}_A \cdot \vec{P}_B. \quad (44)$$

Integration of both sides constitutes (43). This derivation is much simpler and of total different character. While the shaky conventional arguments based on (41) appear to rely on some specific interplay of currents and fields within the MAME, the foundation by (44) exploits the linearity of the CR on a trivial level. It is a part of the intricate DWBA state that the RT (43) is correct, whereas, however, its proof in the DWBA literature is not. Our simpler proof helps to strip off unclear and poorly discussed UP arguments in the DWBA literature and simplify the theoretical approach to its core. When the diffuse ballast of the DWBA is cleared, the specific settings and assumptions of the DWBA can be carved out more explicitly and the comparison to other theories becomes possible. It is an advantage, that our simpler proof fits to the hierarchical approach in the optics literature, where the RP and the RI are established in a separate step within the derivation of the MAME from the MIME, and scattering theories are based exclusively on the MAME and the CRs.

6.7 A Central Assumption of the DWBA

For an application of the RT (43), the DWBA inserts the DD of a pretended unit dipole

$$\vec{P}_A(\vec{r}) = \delta(\vec{R}) - \vec{r} \hat{e} \quad (45)$$

at the location \vec{R} of the detector in the direction of the unit vector \hat{e} (see⁵ after equation (4.9)). The goal is to get rid of an integration in (43) by conjuring a delta function $\delta(\cdot)$. The approach is highly problematic. The detector is located in vacuum with $\vec{\epsilon}_r \equiv 1$. There is neither a dipole nor a polarization of matter in a vacuum. One has $\vec{P}_A(\vec{R}) = \epsilon_0(\vec{\epsilon}_r - 1)\vec{E}_A(\vec{R}) = 0$ at the detector. This result is based on the standard CR. The DWBA ad-hoc equation (45) is not compatible with standard electromagnetism. It can be pointed out, that one of the central assumptions of the DWBA is that one can arbitrarily invent a dipole in vacuum. Once more the approach appears to be inspired by the X-ray specific construction of a RI with the uncontrolled intermixing of microscopic oscillating charges and macroscopic averaged quantities. The poorly discussed UP-approach (45) is not suitable for a scattering theory for visible light, which is based exclusively on a mathematical usage of the MAME and the CRs.

As a further problem of (45), the units of the dipole are not correct. On the other hand, \vec{P}_B , is interpreted as DD in a rough interface layer with correct polarization unit. Equation (4.10) in⁵ which result from an insertion of these \vec{P}_A and \vec{P}_B in (43) is ugly from an optics point of view, as the units on the left and the right sides do not match. Subsequently, the right side of equation (4.11) in⁵ adds up quantities of different units. Equations with different units are possible in case the numerical values on both sides are zero. Like already in (41), the DWBA constructs equations of the form $0 = 0$, obscures this trivial content by complex manipulations which resemble mathematics, and pretends that the results on this basis would be well settled. There is a clear difference between proper mathematics on one hand and the UP within the DWBA on the other hand. The related discussion for equation (76) in the review article⁶ tries to avoid the problem with the units and denotes \vec{E}_A as Green's function with different units as the electrical field. The intermixing of (43) with genuine electric fields and E_A which is interpreted as a Green's function without a proper discussion is far from clear. It remains, that (45) is an ad-hoc assumption and a UP argument not compatible with the CR. Its insufficient discussion disguises the non-mathematical character of these opportunistic manipulations.

An elucidating insight became clear during the critical investigation of the DWBA. The problematic equations (42) and (45) do not carry representative numbers in the original literature⁵. Here is a clear difference to other physics literature. A proper discussion of concepts and assumptions in other physics literature has the consequence, that any key equation does carry a number and is discussed properly. Other not numbered equations might appear only for some trivial transformations. With the sneaky involvement of problematic steps in not numbered equations, the DWBA palms off dubious transformations on its advocators as well as on critical scientists. The former welcome such an approach within their BOC, while the clarification is pushed outside their business. The absence of representative numbers for important equations shows on a formal text structure level, that it is a justified claim that the discussion of the concepts and approximations in the DWBA is on a very poor level.

It is important at this point to emphasize that this discussion is done within the WDRGXRCGA-approach. It is of course up to the

X-ray community alone to intermix a microscopic approach with a macroscopic description at will in their DWBA, fiddle around with dipoles or currents of unclear character and direction which are assumed in a vacuum, introduce symbols in a different meaning than the one which is well established in standard electromagnetism, set up DWBA equations with different units on the left and the right side, and avoid a proper discussion of all these settings within their UP style. Of course they can celebrate the resulting DWBA as their well established theory for X-rays. It should be clear, however, that such approaches are not suitable for a proper interface scattering theory for visible light. Any giddy claim that these peculiar X-ray approaches could be easily transferred to visible light should be avoided. A scientific priority claim based on such particular DWBA procedures over a interface scattering theory for visible light like the ETMA with different mathematics is by no means justified.

6.8 The Elephant in the Room

A theory for interface scattering of visible light should be built up exclusively on the MAME and the CRs. This combination is well accepted for more than a century for the description of classical optical phenomena. It establishes a complete set of equations among four electromagnetic fields \vec{E} , \vec{D} , \vec{H} , and \vec{B} . The simplest case considers dielectric materials with $\vec{J}_{\text{free}} = 0$ and $\rho_{\text{free}} = 0$. As these materials are transparent for light, they are of main interest for optics. The brief discussion at the beginning of section 6.6 elucidates that the concept of the GEDF²⁷ allows a mapping for $\omega \neq 0$ of a system with $\vec{J}_{\text{free}} \neq 0$ and $\rho_{\text{free}} \neq 0$ to a system with $\vec{J}_{\text{free}} = 0$ and $\rho_{\text{free}} = 0$ with a complex RP. It is a mathematical transformation without physics assumptions. In case \vec{J}_{free} is needed, it is calculated by the inverse mapping which corresponds to (40). The continuity equation subsequently yields ρ_{free} . Thus, a speculation about the behavior of the electrons is neither required nor useful. Such a theory is also useful for small angle X-ray scattering when the X-ray RI is established and a MAME approach is suitable. The theory should use proper mathematical arguments and Born's approximation in a well-defined way. So, one needs a clear indication, which contrast is assumed to be small and which terms are neglected. The ETMA fulfills these criteria. The DWBA, in contrast, has additional input. Section 6.7 has shown, that the assumption of an oscillating dipole or a point-like polarization described by a δ -function at the location of the detector where one has $\vec{e}_r = 1$ is not compatible with the CR. The derivation of the DWBA thus postulates an electromagnetic field which can not exist due to its conflicting properties. Clearly, the DWBA's derivation of its Green's function is not a mathematical proof. As, however, the DWBA's discussion is quite nontransparent, the contradiction is rather obscured. Moreover, in a conceptually clear scattering theory which emulates the experiment, the only role of the detector is to measure the intensity of the electromagnetic radiation. The discussion of a polarization at the detector in the DWBA is quite strange.

Sure enough, the opportunistic approach comes to a different conclusion. The X-ray community has a long tradition within the DWBA to consider oscillating electrons as source terms. It

is the WET approach, which repeatedly uses the RI construction for X-rays within the derivation of the DWBA. We saw it also in the conventional derivation of the RT in section 6.6. The CRs are not particularly highlighted in the DWBA-literature, although they are implicitly also used. Within their BOC, it can be expected that X-ray researchers do not mind much about a contradiction to the CRs. WDRGXRCGA it can be asserted that the application of electromagnetic equations is different in optics on one hand and in the X-ray community on the other hand. This finding is the elephant in the room, which nobody dares to mention. It resolves the FAC: the reference to X-rays in the titles of the DWBA literature (see beginning of section 6.2) relates to the WET, X-ray specific approach to electromagnetism. Although this setting is not discussed properly in the DWBA-literature, it is clear that a naive transfer to visible light as it is found within the ME is not appropriate. For visible light, the derivation of the RP²⁶ which determines the RI is different from X-rays, and a contradiction to the CRs in a theory is not acceptable.

We advocate a univocal, mathematics oriented usage of classical electromagnetism like in optics. This approach implies that the DWBA is considered an effective theory without proper mathematical derivation so far. Of course, this statement is done within the WDRGXRCGA mindset. We respect, that for X-ray researchers the continuation of their DWBA tradition might be of much higher value than a well defined and unique approach to electromagnetism.

We indicate already, that the layer scalar product¹³ (10) plays an essential role in the ETMA. It is applied to project RI fluctuations in a layer of the layered profile to suitable field components. There is no corresponding construction in the DWBA. So the mathematics is clearly different. When the blocking of a proper interface scattering theory by DWBA-campaigners is resolved and a publication of the ETMA has become possible, one can insert the SRID conditions to the ETMA and search for a new derivation of the DWBA which contains a proper discussion of the required approximations. It can replace the contradictory and inconsistent derivation of the GF in the DWBA.

6.9 Relevance of the Amplitude Divergence at CC for the DWBA Discussion

The topic of the present work¹ is the divergence of amplitude coefficients in an interface layer on a mathematical level. A connection to experimental results observed by interface scattering of visible light in a TR geometry is established (see section 4). In the examples, the divergence mechanism provides the dominant contribution for interface light scattering. It is furthermore demonstrated, that the divergence mechanism is much weaker for the SRID conditions found in X-rays (see section 3.5). Moreover, we outlined that the low spatial coherence of a X-ray synchrotron source limits the process of accumulation of a wave front to build up the divergence at CC (see section 3.4). These findings suggest, that there are two contributions to an interface scattering signal for a TR geometry: a critical one and a non-critical one. The DWBA reasonably describes the non-critical contribution for the SRID conditions found for X-rays. There is no discussion of CC

in the DWBA. So it does not contain the critical contribution. As this contribution is weak for SRID conditions, the DWBA is successful for X-rays. For visible light in a TR-geometry with significantly larger contrast, however, the critical contribution provides the dominant effect. The restricted DWBA is useless for this case. The new ETMA describes both contributions and thus allows a detailed investigation. As a prerequisite for its usage, it is required to overcome the blocking by the DWBA-campaigners and publish the ETMA. The indication and resolution of the FAC in the present discussion prepares the grounding. It might be required to repeat the arguments of this outlook in an extended form within a full paper. Still, it is of value to establish in the present work the connection between the mathematical divergence of the amplitude at CC, experimental findings which fit to the mechanism, and this outlook that the poorly analyzed but systematically overrated DWBA, for which we acknowledge with good grace that it is a well established theory for X-ray interface scattering, does not include the divergence effects. The naive claim of the X-ray community that the DWBA could be transferred to visible light is not justified based on the matching of the mathematical divergence and the discussed interface light scattering experiments.

The author had discussions on how to overcome the blocking of a proper interface light scattering theory by DWBA advocates with peers as well with the artificial intelligence Claude. They pointed out experimental results which are explained by the new theory but not by the DWBA. A correct prediction of interface light scattering by the ETMA is a first point. Differences to DWBA predictions are particularly expected for p-polarization or a TR-geometry. Especially useful are results which are important also to other scientists. Here, an extension of the brief discussion in section 4.4 on the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) mechanism in a coming publication might be useful. It can be expected, that an acceptance by conventional SPR opinion leaders will be as restrained as the deprecatory reaction of DWBA proponents on the ETMA. However, there are a number of advantages of the CC mechanism over the classical SPR description. The latter starts with a discussion of conditions under which the assumed SP could be generated in a metallic interface layer³¹⁻³³. Similar to the X-ray approach to electromagnetism, such a postulated SP is based on a speculation about the behavior of the electrons in the metallic interface layer. The illumination of the interface by an evanescent wave is identified as essential condition to excite these electrons. There is no further description on how such a SP would lead to an enhanced absorption or scattering. In fact, the need for an additional theory has been recognized by H. Raether³¹, one of the pioneers of SPR. To our knowledge, he did not publish such a theory which he had announced in his textbook³¹. The amplification via CC is different from the conventional SPR model. Our discussion of the CC mechanism provides line widths (see section 3.6) and line shapes for SHG measurements. These predictions are beyond the conventional SPR model. Furthermore, the complex RP is sufficient to characterize the metallic interface layer and no additional speculation about the behavior of its electrons is required. So, the CC mechanism describes the phenomenology of the so-called SPR based exclusively on the MAME and the CR without additional assumptions.

6.10 The Second Key Question

The critical investigation of the DWBA in this outlook is a bit unusual. It is a rather unconventional process that the literature and a textbook on a theory are critically analyzed by an author who has no vested interest in this theory. There is hardly any exemplar in the literature on how such an approach is supposed to be written. Any referee remark that the approach would not be according to scientific writing standards is not appropriate, as there is no writing standard established so far for such a case. Rather, the outlook of the present work could become a role model for similar unclear literature situations.

The discussion here is based on mathematical arguments, physics conceptions, experimental results, and literature content. Thus, the very same elements as in every physics publication are used. A further element of a publication concerns the motivation which outlines, how the content of a publication contributes to a scientific progress. It is the motivation of this outlook which might not fall into a conventional scheme. WDRGXRCGA, this work clarifies that the DWBA is an effective theory for the scattering of X-rays at an interface. The DWBA's mathematical issues and assumptions beyond the combination of MAME and CRs are analyzed. A phenomenological description of the correlation of the poor state of the literature discussion and the uncritical overrating of this theory by DWBA-campaigners characterizes the present state. An extension of the DWBA to other radiation is not appropriate, neither from its shaky theoretical derivation, nor from experiments. Unfortunately, there is the peculiar ME, so persistent and aggressive claims by X-ray researchers that the DWBA would predict also interface scattering experiments with visible light without that they have corresponding data. Such behavior is highly irrational. The regular occurrence of the ME indicates, that the conceptions and approximations in the DWBA have not been discussed so far with sufficient clarity that X-ray researchers would be reliably aware of them.

The second key question which emerges from these considerations concerns the right style and the right location for a publication of the critical DWBA analysis. The relevance of such thoughts becomes clear from a previous attempt to publish this manuscript in the journal *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* (PCCP). This journal advertises a first decision time of 34 days for a peer reviewed manuscript. In our case it took 133 days, almost 4 times as long. The referees' comments hardly addressed the main part of the paper. For the outlook, one referee showed strong interest in a clarification on the FAC, while two others argued in an undifferentiated and vague way that the very first version of our critical analysis would be ranting against the X-ray community. The outlook was substantially revised and expressed much more carefully for the resubmission of the manuscript. Unfortunately, the editor rejected the manuscript with only one second round referee comment. It originated from the referee which had been positive in the first round and who once more expressed a positive confirmation. As such a combination appeared not conclusive, a kind request for transparency in the editorial decision was sent by e-mail. An extended correspondence evolved. At the end, the editor referred to the editorial policy of PCCP that all published

material is aimed to be respectful. The ranting-accusation from the first round tipped the scales and the substantial revision was not acknowledged.

A first conclusion from this previous experience is, that the emphasis of the WDRGXRCGA-approach within this completely rewritten outlook is of much higher relevance than any mathematical argument. It is of high importance to emphasize the high respect for the X-ray community and their DWBA. We furthermore acknowledge that the scientific editors are the gatekeepers for new scientific insight to be published. Of course we respect, that the vague FAC is a highly convenient approach for the X-ray community. The WET character of the DWBA which repeatedly refers to oscillating electrons which originate from the X-ray approach to the RI and which intermixes the microscopic and the macroscopic picture is a highly efficient way to obscure the DWBA's mathematical issues. It is possible, that a physics theory without mathematical consistency successfully describes experiments. We respect that the X-ray community hypes their DWBA, even though it is insufficiently analyzed. It is, of course, up to the X-ray researchers only to decide on the scattering theory with which they analyze their valuable data.

Beyond such due respect, it is a basic requirement in science, that terms are defined properly. Such a clear definition of terms usually precedes any other scientific work. It is the very basis of scientific work. In mathematical derivations a proper display of premises is indispensable. The necessity of the discussion in this outlook comes from the vagueness of the FAC and poorly discussed assumptions and transformations in the DWBA literature. Poorly introduced terms like the DD constitute an essential terminology vagueness, which renders a compressive discussion impossible. The naive approach of X-ray researchers that the DWBA is suitable for visible light without that they have a proper understanding that the SRID conditions valid for X-rays are no longer fulfilled, and without that they have suitable data, is a severe problem. The text here comes as a reaction on the BOC, so the correlation of the poor DWBA literature state and the systematic overrating of this theory by X-ray researchers which generates the ME. Ideally, one could expect also respect from members of the X-ray community to theoretical work for interface scattering of visible light and new theoretical work in general. If such an ideal state can not be reached, it is time to anchor in the literature that there are quite opposite assessments of the DWBA. While the X-ray community adores it, our analysis unveiled mathematical and conceptual weaknesses of this theory. Our qualified DWBA-critics should not be misinterpreted as ranting against the X-ray community. The quest for proper terms and clarified assumptions should not be mistaken as disrespect.

Furthermore, we acknowledge that this DWBA analysis is difficult to review. It is unavoidable, that a critical look on an unclear and poorly discussed theory becomes rather technical. The uncommon approach to scrutinize a theory with vague content inevitably requires an uncommon style, which is different from standard publications. The complexity of the topic, however, should not be a reason for rejection. Instead, it is essential to recognize that a critical analysis of the DWBA is overdue. It is a part of scientific content in general that it has to suffer per-

manently a critical reviewing. One can expect, that the topic is controversial and will not be appreciated by a part of the X-ray community. However, any attempt for a preservation of vested rights is not appropriate for scientific work. The argument, that the DWBA has to be considered a great theory just for the reason that it is described in a textbook¹⁴ is such an attempt. The same applies for the ME.

The critical review of the DWBA is discussed already in scientific conferences. It is time, that this discussion finds its way to the scientific literature. A rejection of thoroughly analyzed scientific content just because of writing style issues, when no writing style for such a situation is established so far, is clearly not appropriate. For a theory, we advocate a clear distinction between its mathematical consistency and its value to describe experiments. In conference discussions so far, some X-ray researchers became bewildered by the DWBA-critics. We calmed them down. For X-rays, the DWBA has become a well established effective theory, so GISAXS users can continue to employ it. It does not matter, that the DWBA derivation so far contains mathematical problems. Due to the SRID condition which leads to negligible gradients with a basically flat RI behavior, it is not surprising, that the GF for the DWBA looks very similar than a GF for a bulk scattering theory. There is furthermore always a free scaling parameter, as interface scattering experiments are not performed on absolute intensities. For these conditions, a deductive derivation of the DWBA with proper indication of the employed approximations from a more general interface scattering theory should be possible. Thus, there is basically no change for GISAXS users. What is new, however, is that our analysis establishes a critical investigation of the DWBA's mathematical issues. Any further ME conflict can be resolved based on this work. In particular the obscuring of the SRID condition which is already contained in the construction of a RI for X-rays (see section 6.3) and the WET character of the DWBA (see section 6.6) are simple but useful arguments.

Finally, we highlight that a proper understanding of the mathematical basis of a physically motivated theory construct is of high scientific value. An example is when a researcher writes a proposal for a scientific grant. Inevitably, such a proposal requires a description of the state of the art. The vague character of the DWBA foundation which is correlated to the overrating of this theory by X-ray researchers renders a proper description of the state impossible. A consensus about the state of the art can not be achieved when the real literature state gets intermingled with the opportunistic illusion of DWBA-advocators. In section 6.1 we saw the unsettling example of an MPI X-ray researcher who insisted in an aggressive way that the DWBA would be suitable for birefringent systems. The DWBA's reference to electrons in matter which behave similar to free charges when they are shaken by the high energy X-rays excludes anisotropic polarizability which is specific to birefringence. Once more we see, that the DWBA literature is not clear enough to inform its proponents in an adequate way. Our critical review clarifies the DWBA's terms, physical concepts, assumptions and issues. So, the state of the art is analyzed and it becomes possible to set up such a research proposal for a scientific grant. It transfers the scientific value to pecuniary research funding. It's high time to publish this critical DWBA anal-

ysis. The overcoming of the naive over-assessment of the DWBA by the X-ray community is expected to fertilize the theoretical development of scattering at interfaces.

6.11 The Key Decision Makers

We end this critical outlook with a very positive aspect. After the 2019 conference presentation¹¹ outlined in section 6.1, two young PhD students or postdocs independently showed strong interest in the ETMA, in contrast to the intrusive chairman. While the DWBA appears to end with its specific integration over a GF where numerical methods are required, the ETMA provides a much simpler and direct calculation of interface scattering with the same straightforwardness as other TMMs. For a new method, it is of higher value to inspire young scientists than to convince narrow-minded representatives of prestigious institutions. It is time to establish our clarifying fencing of the DWBA in order to overcome the blocking of new interface scattering theories by opportunistic DWBA-campaigners.

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